

COMMUNITY ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT BASED ON DIGITAL IN BETAK VILLAGE, KALIDAWIR DISTRICT, TULUNGAGUNG REGENCY

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ABSTRACT

Obstacles that hinder MSMEs from developing well in the fields of marketing and financial management include: in terms of ability which includes inadequate educational background, never having participated in accounting training and from the perspective of business actors there is no need for accounting implementation according to (Elisabeth, 2020). The training began by providing motivation to MSMEs on how important it is to study and understand and get the benefits of financial reports for MSMEs (Subiyantoro, 2017). Meanwhile, the obstacles faced by MSMEs in Betak Village at this time, especially regarding financial management, are: 1) low education and lack of knowledge about how to manage finances and make good financial records, 2) lack of understanding of the use of technology and information that helps make financial records, 3) have never participated in adequate accounting training, 4) and do not know the information technology that can be used to help manage finances. One example of the community service that we do is the MSME producing Mrs. Erni's chocolate. The chocolate business which has become one of the products of Betak Village, Tulungagung Regency, one of the attractions which is a typical superior of East Java Province, which experiences obstacles in marketing. In 2023, there are 100 MSMEs in Betak village that are running traditionally. Seeing the marketing and financial recording models that are still very simple and only record income, the Team provides assistance in developing online (digital)-based businesses, both in terms of marketing and financial reporting. The potential in Betak Kalidawir village has begun to be mapped. This data collection can be a reference for a road map for community service in the MSME community of Betak Kalidawir village, Tulungagung, in order to make service sustainable. On the marketing side, in addition to being recommended to be digitally based through brand assistance, in order to organize business branding to be able to increase marketing reach such as: brand assistance, risk-based NIB licensing assistance, halal product process assistance, financial report assistance, marketing assistance through product branding.

Keywords: *Community, Economic, Empowerment, Digital*

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are the pillars of the Indonesian economy, as evidenced by the ability of MSMEs to save the economy in Indonesia during the monetary crisis in 1998. There has been a significant increase in the number of MSMEs in Indonesia, inseparable from the problems that cause the failure of MSME actors. Among those that influence simple management factors, lack of supervision of production processes and quality caused by the system in the entity, simple recording of financial reports, and limited market access. Hapsari et al. (2016) in their research explained that the results of a survey of 45 respondents found that only 51% of respondents who ordered business and those in accordance with creditor needs were only 15.5%.

This is a factor causing the small percentage of MSMEs that record in accordance with stakeholder needs because they are not used to recording and their poor understanding of financial statements. Therefore, it can be seen that MSMEs really need simple tools to help market their products. The results of the researcher's interview with the owner can conclude that MSMEs in Betak Tulungagung have tried to market their products as evaluation material for the owner, also intended for external parties who need them. However, MSMEs in Betak Tulungagung are constrained by human resources and digital marketing knowledge that can market community products so that they can compete in the modern market. MSMEs in Betak Village, Tulungagung do not prepare financial reports based on because since the establishment of MSMEs, until now, they have been constrained by knowledge and Human Resources (HR) in preparing financial reports. We already know that marketing and financial reports are very important elements for the sustainability of businesses carried out by MSMEs in Betak Kalidawir Village, Tulungagung Regency.

With the presence of researchers, it is hoped that it can facilitate MSMEs in Betak Village in compiling practical digital-based financial report marketing strategies, so that the existence of simple financial reports can make it easier for MSMEs to know their performance and can significantly increase the development of MSMEs in Betak Village. In addition, assistance will be provided for marketing and simple digital-based financial reports to be able to compete in the modern market.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are one of the business units that play an important role and have a major influence on the development of the Indonesian economy. "The number of MSME actors is 64.2 million or 99.99% of the total number of business actors in Indonesia. The absorption capacity of MSME workers is 117 million workers or 97% of the absorption capacity of the business world's workforce, which means that MSMEs can absorb more workers than even large companies. This is because large companies utilize technology more than human labor. From this phenomenon, it can be seen that MSMEs are productive businesses that have a significant influence in helping economic growth in Indonesia.

From the definition and criteria of MSMEs above, in general, a similar thread can be drawn regarding MSMEs. First, in terms of wealth, MSMEs tend to be entities that have a net worth of no less than IDR 10 billion. Second, MSMEs are business units whose capital also relies more on personal capital structures or at a more advanced level has used assistance from small business credit. Third, in general, MSMEs do not yet have legal status. Fourth, the MSME industry group is still limited to business groups that tend to be simple.

OECD in Mazzarol, Reboud, and Clark (2022), states that the sources of funding for MSMEs are capital, debt, and retained earnings. Capital is funds invested by the owner to increase the company's productivity and profitability in the future. Debt is a loan given by a third party to the company, with interest obligations as income received by the creditor. The debt repayment period can be long-term or short-term depending on the agreed agreement. Retained earnings are part of the profit used to increase the company's capital.

Funding is one of the main obstacles faced by MSMEs. Research conducted by Abdulsaleh and Worthington (2013) states that company size, length of time the company has been established, type of ownership, legality, location, company sector, and asset composition are factors that influence company funding. However, several studies explain that MSMEs prioritize personal capital over loans from third parties (Hamilton and Fox, 1998; Adair and Adaskou, 2011).

2.2 Marketing Cycle

Kotler and Armstrong define marketing as a social or management process that allows individuals or groups to get what they want. Namely by finding something through the exchange of values or products with other parties. Kotler states marketing is a social and managerial process whereby individuals and groups obtain what they need and want through creating and exchanging products and value with others (Usman: 2020). The main idea in marketing can be seen from the exchange process in marketing management which can be formulated more clearly, namely the analysis, planning, implementation, and control of the program design for the exchange of goods with the desired party, either for personal purposes or to gain profit. (Kotler and Ziehlman: 1971).

Quoting Adnan, there are three important dimensions in the definition of conventional marketing, namely: First, social interaction that only occurs when there are buyers and sellers, Second: the success of the interaction is determined by a good understanding of the concept of needs, desires, demands, products, values, satisfaction, quality, markets and so on, and Third: the ultimate goal of marketing is to achieve individual and organizational satisfaction (Usman: 2020). Thus, marketing activities are activities to fulfill human desires through value exchange activities. Because it is a desire, it can continue until the desire is achieved. Human desires tend to develop and are difficult to predict and translate. The definition of Sharia marketing according to Hermawan and Sula is a business process whose entire process applies Islamic values, honesty, and justice. Meanwhile, Alom and Haque make a similar but more detailed definition by considering spiritual wealth in the

world and the hereafter, such as wisdom, halal, and welfare (falah) of sellers and buyers (Usman: 2020). Then simply put, sharia marketing has the meaning, "A process to meet needs through the creation or exchange of products and values that are guided by sharia." The fundamental difference between conventional marketing and Sharia marketing also lies in the motivational drive that underlies the creation, transaction, or exchange. Conventional marketing is more directed at fulfilling desires while sharia marketing prioritizes achieving needs. As stated by Al Faruqi and Qardhawi who stated that in Islam a person should consume based on their needs (Usman: 2020). These needs are also grouped into levels, some of which are urgent (dharani), basic (hajiyat), and complementary (tahsiniyat). Therefore, the principle of wisdom in responding to something is highly recommended in Islam so as not to fall into excessive or futile things. There are four characteristics of sharia marketing, as stated by Hermawan and Sula (Usman: 2020), First. Spiritualistic, namely the source of business behavior must be based or coherent in the Qur'an and Sunnah. Second, Ethics or akhlaqul karma means that marketing and marketer actions based on Islamic teachings (the Qur'an and Hadith) will form Islamic ethics in business transactions. Third. Realistically, even though the Qur'an and Hadith are absolute provisions, at certain times they can be flexible in their implementation. Therefore, Sharia marketing should not be rigid, as long as it does not violate Islamic law. Office Channelling is one example, namely utilizing banking technology services for important and urgent needs. And fourth, humanism is a view of humans or human interests as the most important object. Islam came as a blessing for nature which means providing great benefits to humanity. Therefore, Sharia marketing must apply the principles of compassion, honesty, and justice. If Sharia marketing applies these characteristics, it will be very ideal and noble. Profit is important, but companies still consider the humanitarian aspect in addition to large profits.

2.3 Financial Reports

According to IAI, "The Financial Accounting Standards for Micro, Small and Medium Entities (SAK EMKM) are prepared to meet the financial reporting needs of micro, small and medium entities. Law No. 20 of 2008 concerning Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises can be used as a reference in defining and providing quantitative ranges for EMKM. This standard is intended for use by entities that are not or have not been able to meet the accounting requirements stipulated in SAK ETAP. SAK EMKM is effective on January 1, 2018. SAK EMKM is intended for micro, small, and medium entities to meet financial reporting needs. Therefore, this SAK is expected to be able to help MSMEs in preparing financial reports because SAK EMKM is designed to be simpler, and adjusted to conditions in MSMEs. However, because it is still mapping, researchers only provide practical digital-based financial reporting assistance to help manage MSME finances in Betak Kalidawir Village, Tulungagung Regency. Perhaps in the future, besides evaluating the journey of MSMEs in Betak Village, there will be a greater emphasis on marketing and financial management.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Problem Solving Framework

Understanding the business fields of MSME actors is important so that community service can provide optimal benefits for MSME actors. Several stages in the community service process in MSMEs in Betak Tulungagung Village and its community are:

1. Preliminary survey in the form of intense communication about mentoring needs.
2. The results of the communication show that the main needs of MSMEs are digital marketing assistance and simple financial records.
3. The community service team creates relevant materials with examples that can be applied by MSMEs in Betak Kalidawir Tulungagung Village.
4. Implementation of community service activities by providing materials and discussing marketing practices and financial records used along with their applications.
5. Evaluation of activities in the form of requests for input from MSMEs in Betak Kalidawir Village regarding obstacles and barriers in the mentoring process.

Conducting training on making digital marketing and digital-based financial reports. The material is arranged in such a way that it is in accordance with the purpose of the service. The delivery of the material is also not rigidly regulated but is completed one by one starting from the introduction, technical recording to the preparation of financial reports. MSME actors are enthusiastic in implementing the activities so that the discussion process runs smoothly and lively. The evaluation process is also carried out by asking open questions about digital marketing and accounting records. The results show that MSME actors generally understand the material provided, but have difficulty in implementing digital marketing and making records due to habits in the administrative process that have been carried out for a long time. Only doing traditional marketing and simple financial recording manually. Income alone without recording the burdens incurred, even many of them run out of capital because they are not orderly and disciplined in managing finances.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

MSME Betak Kalidawir village Tulungagung is one of the MSMEs that has a fairly high development potential. The products produced by UMKM are Chocolate, Clothes Hangers, Koi ornamental fish, Patin fish and various other products.

Figure 1 Digital Marketing Training

The management process is also carried out using halal ingredients. This is proven by the management of halal assistance by the FE UIN Malang Community Service Team which is trying to be internalized in UMKM Pia RB. UMKM Pia RB is committed to forming a halal management team and seriously implementing all operational procedures. The following Figure 2 shows the process of making Pia RB with Halal ingredients.

Figure 2 Digital-based Financial Reporting Training

MSME Actors in Betak Kalidawir Village, Tulungagung Regency

4.1 Digital Financial Reports

The purpose of financial reports according to SAK EMKM is to create simple financial reports that can be used by stakeholders in making decisions related to MSMEs. Simple digital-based financial reports are proven by only three financial reports that must be created, namely the balance sheet, income statement, and notes to the financial statements. The balance sheet is a financial report that presents information about the assets, liabilities, and equity of an entity at the end of the reporting period. Assets are resources controlled by an entity as a result of past events and from which future economic benefits are expected to be obtained by the entity. Liabilities are present obligations of the entity arising from past events, the settlement of which results in an outflow from the entity of resources containing economic benefits. Equity is the residual right to the entity's assets after deducting all its liabilities. The minimum accounts in the balance sheet that must be present are Cash and cash equivalents, Receivables, Inventories, Fixed assets, Accounts payable, Bank loans, and Equity.

Figure 4. Shows a balance sheet that can be used by MSMEs in Betak Village.

ENTITAS LAPORAN POSISI KEUANGAN 31 DESEMBER 20X8			
ASET	Catatan	20X8	20X7
Kas dan setara kas			
Kas	3	xxx	xxx
Giro	4	xxx	xxx
Deposito	5	xxx	xxx
Jumlah kas dan setara kas		xxx	xxx
Piutang usaha			
Persediaan	6	xxx	xxx
Beban dibayar di muka	7	xxx	xxx
Aset tetap		xxx	xxx
Akumulasi penyusutan		(xx)	(xx)
JUMLAH ASET		xxx	xxx
LIABILITAS			
Utang usaha		xxx	xxx
Utang bank	8	xxx	xxx
JUMLAH LIABILITAS		xxx	xxx
EKUITAS			
Modal		xxx	xxx
Saldo laba (defisit)	9	xxx	xxx
JUMLAH EKUITAS		xxx	xxx
JUMLAH LIABILITAS & EKUITAS		xxx	xxx

The next report that must be made by UMKM Desa Betak Kalidawir is the profit and loss report. The Profit and Loss Report presents information on the entity's financial performance which includes Income and Expenses. Income is an increase in economic benefits during the reporting period in the form of cash inflows or increases in assets, or decreases in liabilities resulting in an increase in equity that does not come from investor contributions. Expenses are a decrease in economic benefits during the reporting period in the form of cash outflows or decreases in assets, or increases in liabilities resulting in a decrease in equity that is not caused by distributions to investors. The minimum accounts in the profit and loss report are Income, Financial expenses, and Tax expenses. Figure 5 shows the profit and loss report that can be made by UMKM Desa Betak

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The activity went smoothly. The main problem of Betak Village MSMEs is Knowledge and HR that do not have sufficient understanding of digital marketing and good accounting so that financial recording is only done in sales recording without recording expenses/burdens. So that it can only describe the traditional sales of Betak Kalidawir Village MSMEs, Tulungagung, without being able to know the developments so far whether there has been progress, profit or not. The financial report of Betak Kalidawir Village MSMEs should be in accordance with general reports, namely balance sheets, profit and loss, and CALK. To facilitate all of this, you can use a digital-based Marketing and Financial Reporting Strategy. In addition, intense and ongoing assistance will be able to help Betak Village MSMEs compete in the modern market.

This activity is very beneficial for MSMEs, in addition to providing refresher courses related to modern marketing and digital-based financial management. MSME actors can also convey their complaints in the financial management process. However, the event which was only held once caused the material not to be absorbed properly. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a follow-up in the form of a discussion on digital marketing and simple financial management of UMKM Betak Village, Kalidawir District, Tulungagung Regency. Wallahu a'alam bi-Shawab.

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